

Workforce Issues in Archaeology and Historic Building Conservation

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This paper presents an overview of workforce development issues facing the historic environment subsector which is intended to partner the document produced by Caitlin Griffiths on workforce issues facing the museum and gallery sector that was presented to the Cultural Heritage Skills Advisory Panel Meeting on 15 June 2006. It is deliberately arranged to mirror that document, using the same subject headings in order to ease comparison, and like it this document flags up priority areas rather addressing all issues in detail.

Archaeology and historic buildings conservation are being addressed together as two professions that share occupational and functional commonalities, and so are likely to also share workforce development issues. These professions are concerned with the interpretation and conservation of physical (and largely non-portable) traces left by human activity in the past, in terms of archaeological sites, landscapes and buildings.

Reliable data on archaeological employment are presented in Archaeology Labour Market Intelligence: Profiling the Profession 2002-03 (Aitchison & Edwards 2003), the results of an extensive sub-sector wide survey. This repeated a 1997-98 survey (Aitchison 1999), and it is intended to be repeated in 2007-08 and through an ongoing five year repetition cycle. There is no single comparable source of data for historic building conservation.

Entry Routes

Aitchison & Edwards (2003, 20) estimated the total number of individuals working in archaeology as approximately 5,700 people in paid archaeological employment across the UK. These individuals are distributed across the public, private and NGO sectors, fulfilling a variety of working roles of field investigation and research, providing advice, museum and visitor services, and educational and academic research. This sector is dominated by micro-businesses: 72 percent of archaeological workplaces have 10 or fewer employees, and only 4 percent have 50 or more (Aitchison & Edwards 2003, 15).

The largest functional area is in field investigation and research, where 49 percent of archaeologists work.

This professional workforce is complemented by approximately 425 volunteers at any given point of time.

While a relatively small profession, professional archaeology has been growing rapidly since the early 1990s and future growth is anticipated (Aitchison & Edwards 2003, 29).

Volunteer opportunities declined significantly between 1997-98 and 2002-03, following changing work-practices in both the commercial and public sectors. Since the late 1960s – early 1970s, when the bulk of archaeological work was undertaken on a voluntary basis, voluntary opportunities have declined with the professionalization of the discipline. Outdated careers advice information and guidance continues to promote volunteering as a route in to the profession; this is effectively no longer a representative entry route.

Currently, entry routes are very limited and competition for posts is intense. In comparison with a workforce of 5,700 in 2002-03, a total of 11,755 students were enrolled on archaeology degree courses in 2003-04 (Ramsden 2005). 90 percent of professional archaeologists are graduates, and 97 percent of those aged in their 20s are (Aitchison & Edwards 2003, 37). A degree has become an informal but de facto entry requirement. With such a current oversupply of graduates pursuing a limited number of vacancies, non-graduates have little chance of gaining entry-level jobs as there is an absence of any other competence- or knowledge criteria being used by employers when sifting applications from candidates.

Increasing numbers of individuals are undertaking taught post-graduate courses before or soon after entering the labour market in order to enhance their employability.

In addition to undergraduate degrees being delivered at over forty establishments, foundation degrees in archaeology are being delivered at only Bournemouth University (Aitchison & Giles 2006, 7). Vocational qualifications in archaeological practice, founded on National Occupational Standards, have been developed and are currently (2006-07) being rolled out. Both of these mechanisms may provide alternative entry routes. There is a high level of enthusiasm for these qualifications, both from individual practitioners and from employers. 66 percent of employers said they would

give 'considerable' or 'very considerable' support to staff in working towards vocational qualifications (Aitchison & Edwards 2003, 59).

Less detailed information on employment and entry routes for historic building conservation is available; this is also a graduate profession, where practitioners enter via a variety of professional and training backgrounds (mainly planning and architecture) and there are very few specific undergraduate courses, and a small number of post-graduate courses (Preston 2002, 8). These courses are reviewed by the Conservation Course Directors' Forum.

The membership of IHBC was approximately 1,450 in 2002 (IHBC 2003); this membership is made up of individuals working in local government, advising planning officers, and others working in the private sector. Membership of this body has effectively become an entry requirement for working in public sector building conservation, and extrapolating from figures presented by Grover (2003) suggests that 1,060 individuals worked in local government historic building conservation in England in 2003.

Diversity

36 percent of professional archaeologists are female, 64 percent male. Before ages 30-39, the gender proportions are equally balanced, with the numbers of women working in archaeology reducing from that point on. It is unknown whether this represents women leaving the profession at this stage in their careers, or whether the numbers of women working in archaeology has started to increase but that this has yet to work its way up the age ranges (Aitchison & Edwards 2003, 22).

Archaeology is not ethnically diverse. 99.3 percent of working archaeologists are white (Aitchison & Edwards 2003, 25); Benjamin (2003) found that 2.03 percent of archaeology undergraduate students were of black or Asian origin.

Archaeology has also had very limited participation by disabled individuals. The proportion of working archaeologists who are disabled (as defined under Disability and Discrimination Act 1995) is only 0.34 percent (Aitchison & Edwards 2003, 25), and in the past (across higher education) the prime focus for disabled students has been on participation and learner support, rather than employability (Aitchison & Giles 2006, 7).

No diversity data are available for the historic building conservation workforce.

Professional Development & Training

Skills shortages and gaps, both in terms of technical and generic, non-archaeological skills have been identified in archaeology (Aitchison & Edwards 2003, 53-57) and these are being used by the Archaeology Training Forum to guide industry wide policy in training provision. This has led to [English Heritage](#) and [Historic Scotland](#) funding ongoing series of one-day courses in professional skills (many facilitated by IFA), and both professional associations run annual conferences and day schools.

Both IFA and IHBC have policies that require members to undertake and self-monitor their own Continuing Professional Development. Both require members to undertake 50 hours of relevant professional development over a rolling two-year period. This is compulsory for IHBC members, but obligatory (in the sense of a professional obligation, rather than a compulsion with penalties for non-compliance) for [IFA](#) members. This is not actively policed and is not well-understood by the professional association's membership.

As these policies are input-based (judged by the amount of time committed) rather than output-based (judged by the learning achievements of the individual member) they can be seen as inflexible, mechanistic approaches to learning that are based on the quantity, rather than the quality, of the learning experiences that individuals undertake.

Specialist Knowledge and Skills

The lack of opportunities for specialist skills transmission in archaeology has been an ongoing issue for some time. Only larger archaeological companies are able to retain finds and environmental specialists on full-time contracts, and so many of these specialists now work on self-employed bases. This often means that they are unable to invest time and financial resources in training the successor generation of specialists, and there is a danger that particular competences will become increasingly short supplied. There are frequent calls for apprentice schemes in these areas.

This is partly being addressed by the [English Heritage](#) EPPIC (English Heritage Professional Placements in Conservation) and [IFA HLF](#) Bursaries scheme, which include addressing these issues within their overall aims.

Both of these schemes will be part of the proposed pilot framework for Creative Apprenticeships within archaeology that [IFA](#) will lead on behalf of [CCSkills](#).

There are also issues of specialists needing to learn the business skills that they require for their working environments; this is not being widely addressed. [English Heritage](#) are proposing to introduce Historic Environment 'Traineeships' where historic environment professionals are cycled through a range of placements.

Career Progression

Early career work in archaeology can be intermittent and short-term, leading to individuals working for a series of employers on short contracts, sometimes with intervening periods of unemployment.

Within private sector archaeology, there are few well-defined career progression routes. Career progression routes are better defined within the public sector, but it is also difficult for individuals to move horizontally within the profession, from one area to another. Lack of career progression opportunities leads to stagnation and loss of staff; a considerable number of people leave archaeology in their mid-20s, when they find their progression a few years after graduation to have not matched their expectations. This loss of people also represents a loss of investment, as all of the

training they have received is lost as they can generally only be replaced by inexperienced new graduates.

As most historic building conservation professionals are within local or national government bodies, career progression routes are relatively well-defined. The substantial private sector element have opportunities to advance across a range of environmental assessment and management routes and there is greater possibility for horizontal movement into the development and planning sector.

Pay

As in the museums and galleries subsector, pay has a significant impact on issues around recruitment, retention and motivation of staff within archaeology.

In 2002-03, the average salary for archaeologists was £19,161, which compared poorly with a national average for full-time workers in all occupations of £24,498 (Aitchison & Edwards 2003, 39).

The **IFA** publishes annual minimum salary guidelines, based on the membership grades of that Institute and linked to points on the local government spinal pay column. Any advertiser appearing to breach these minima will be investigated and on occasion challenged by the Institute, but the organisation does not have any binding mandate over non-members.

An annual review of jobs advertised is published by the **IFA**; the figures for 2005 (Drummond-Murray 2006) show that 210 jobs were advertised, with salary data available for 127 of these, giving an average salary of £18,158. However, it is worth noting that very few junior fieldworker jobs were advertised. These are normally filled by speculative application to employers.

No salary data are available for building conservation.

Conclusions

Both archaeology and historic building conservation face critical workplace issues in terms of entry routes, diversity, continuing professional development and specialist skills. Within historic building conservation, there is a need for reliable labour market information as currently we actually know and understand very little about the building conservation sector, its perception of itself and its aspirations.

The industries have begun engagement with the skills-based issues of CPD and specialisms, but a great deal of further commitment needs to be demonstrated by stakeholders to realistically progress these.

Entry routes and diversity have been largely ignored by the industries. This has led to a situation where these industries could be seen as socially exclusive and non-meritocratic, with many potentially good people being denied opportunities to establish themselves and to professionally advance within them.

These industries urgently need robust, competence-based benchmarks to be applied in order to support their meritocratic development. National Occupational Standards do exist in both archaeological practice (Carter & Robertson 2002) and building conservation management (Rolfe 2004), but their use needs to be actively implemented and supported.

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